

Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM) on Learners' Vocabulary Skills in Physics

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Abstract

The Philippines has consistently ranked low in science in the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA). In the PISA 2022 results, only 23% of Filipino students achieved basic proficiency in science, highlighting significant challenges in the science education system. Moreover, the results of the Regional Diagnostic Assessment for Grades 7 and 8 learners at John J. Russell Memorial High School identified the least learned competencies in physics topics. This prompted researchers to develop a strategy called Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM), aimed at enhancing learners' vocabulary in physics to help them comprehend difficult terms and complex concepts more easily. The study employed a multiphase mixed-method design. Two heterogeneous sections from Grade 7 were selected as respondents through purposive sampling techniques. A validated, researcher-made image-based mnemonic was used as a strategy for teaching physics. Before each lesson, the corresponding Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM) were displayed on the board to engage students. During discussions, the images were analyzed and interpreted to aid comprehension. The experimental group used IBM four times a week, covering three major physics topics in the third quarter. The mean score in the post-test of the experimental group was higher ($M = 21.522$, $SD = 2.83$) than that of the control group ($M = 14.560$, $SD = 2.28$). The computed absolute t-values in the results of the comparative-based questions ($t = -32.000$, $t = -13.525$), which were both significantly higher than the t-critical, and the p-values, both at $p = 0.000$, indicate that the experimental group demonstrated significant improvement upon exposure to IBM. These suggest that the use of image-based mnemonics has a highly promising impact on enhancing learners' vocabulary skills in physics. Additionally, the learners' responses to the interview guide revealed high satisfaction and enjoyment in the learning process upon exposure to IBM. These findings were further supported by their perceptions, concluding that the integration of image-based mnemonics in science classes was beneficial, enjoyable, and motivating for learners.

Keywords: *Action Research, Physics, Competency, Image-Based Mnemonics, Vocabulary Skills, Visual Learners*

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Introduction

Vocabulary skills in science refer to students' ability to understand and use scientific terms effectively. This includes not only memorizing definitions but also grasping the specific language and terminology unique to the scientific domain. Students are expected to go beyond rote memorization and comprehend how these words are interconnected, how they are used in different scientific situations, and how they contribute to a deeper understanding of scientific concepts.

Even though science vocabulary is regularly taught in classrooms, an observation at John J. Russell Memorial High School in October and November 2023 revealed an interesting finding. The researchers, during their field study, observed that despite the teaching efforts, some Grade 7 students faced difficulties in fully understanding the concepts being taught. This observation raises questions about the effectiveness of current teaching methods and highlights the necessity for personalized strategies to improve students' vocabulary acquisition, ensuring a stronger foundation for students to better grasp scientific concepts.

Given the broad nature of the science field, the researchers consulted the results of the Regional Diagnostic Assessment (RDA) for Grade 7 and 8 students during the school year 2023-2024, which aimed to provide a better insight into the specific areas of science where students struggled the most. Upon examination, the researchers then identified the least learned competencies in science among both Grade 7 and 8 students.

The RDA results of Grade 7 students in science, with components anchored to the science lessons in their sixth grade and taken by 529 students, revealed that among the topics, one from physics showed noticeably low correct responses, i.e., energy transformation (Rank 1) and friction and gravity (Rank 2 and 8). These indicate that the competencies anchored to them were among the least learned competencies in Science 7.

However, since Grade 7 students' RDA results in science were anchored to their science lessons in the previous school year, the researchers then considered those of Grade 8 students, with components anchored to the science lessons in their seventh grade. With a total of 504 takers, the results showed that among the topics, five from physics showed noticeably low correct responses, i.e., electricity (Rank 1), light (Rank 3), sound (Rank 4), heat transfer (Rank 6), and motion (Rank 8 and 9). These indicate that the competencies anchored to them were among the least learned competencies in Science 8.

Understanding specialized terminology is a crucial element in physics education (Chakrabarti, 2019). Physics, being a discipline that heavily rests on specific and precise terminology, requires students to grasp this language efficiently for a comprehensive understanding of the concepts (Drummond, 2019). However, students often encounter difficulties with physics vocabulary, which can impede their overall understanding of the subject (Latifa, Purwaningsih, & Sutopo, 2021). Therefore, it is crucial to explore and implement strategies that can effectively improve students' vocabulary skills in physics.

Mnemonic methods have long been acknowledged for their effects on memory and recall. Research suggests that mnemonics can significantly enhance the retention and recall of information, including vocabulary (Tullis, 2021). Therefore, incorporating mnemonic strategies can potentially boost students' ability to understand and remember physics vocabulary. Additionally, images can also be a powerful tool in learning. According to the Dual-Coding Theory, information is easier to remember when presented both verbally and visually (Guitard & Cowan, 2020). This suggests that integrating images into mnemonic methods—i.e., creating image-based mnemonics—could further enhance students' vocabulary skills in Physics.

Furthermore, research in cognitive psychology suggests that the use of visual imagery can aid in memory retention and recall. By leveraging the visual processing capabilities of the brain, image-based mnemonics can potentially reduce cognitive load and facilitate the encoding and retrieval of new vocabulary terms. In the context of physics education, where students are often introduced to a wide array of domain-specific terminology, the use of image-based mnemonic strategies may offer a promising approach to support vocabulary acquisition.

To address the stated problem and considering all the information previously mentioned, the researchers utilized an image-based mnemonic—a technique aiding in memorizing related items by associating a mental picture with a fact or piece of information. This was considered because students appreciate the idea of visualizing lessons (Damiri, Hastomo, & Sari, 2022), making the use of images as a tool in improving students' vocabulary skills worth considering.

Various image mnemonics related to specific physics vocabularies were created and incorporated into the teaching-learning process. These image mnemonics were intentionally ridiculous and odd, as research indicates that such an approach is helpful for information to be remembered more easily, and these mental images can enhance recall performance when compared with standard learning instructions (Runge, Craig, & Jim, 2015).

Additionally, the image-based mnemonics used were integrated into the lesson plan and became part of the actual teaching-learning process. The repeated use of these mnemonics aims to reinforce cognitive processes and strengthen the connections between new information and existing mental structures (Mountstephens, 2020).

In relation to this, Grade 7 marks a critical stage in students' cognitive and linguistic development, a period characterized by increased cognitive abilities and the maturation of abstract thinking (Nilson, 2023). Given the importance of vocabulary development in mastering scientific concepts, exploring the effectiveness of image-based mnemonics specifically tailored to the language of physics at this developmental stage is particularly relevant.

That being the case, this study was conducted to investigate the effects of Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM) on Grade 7 learners' vocabulary skills in physics. The results of this study could then provide valuable insights into developing more effective teaching strategies in physics education and broaden the understanding of how students learn and remember complex physics concepts.

Literature Review

Numerous studies have suggested and found that mnemonic strategies, highlighted for their effectiveness in facilitating learning and memory, stand out as valuable tools for mastering unfamiliar and challenging information, in contrast to other techniques more geared toward storing information.

Mnemonics, techniques utilized to enhance memory retention, play a crucial role in aiding individuals to remember information more effectively. According to Tullis (2021), mnemonics serve as memory aids by facilitating the encoding and recall of important information. Originating from ancient Greece, the basic principles of mnemonics have evolved over time, continually refined to suit modern needs. Presently, a diverse array of mnemonic methods is employed, spanning from straightforward acronyms to intricate strategies like converting numbers into memorable phrases (Qizi, 2023).

Educators are encouraged to mold learners into critical thinkers, and in line with this goal, image mnemonics is the strategy that has a potential to be easily modified and incorporated in teaching which can be modified not to solely memorize words but also interpret word's meaning through images (Inal, 2021).

Visual mnemonics, or image-based mnemonics, are widely used to provide meaning and information; in addition, it is also used to cater to the interests and needs of the learners. Through this method, the meanings of a particular word become clear (Lestari, 2017).

In relation to images, Harper (2018) found that using word groups, pictures, and different visual tools helps students understand scientific words better. When terms are shown visually and connected to the main idea, students can make their own connections, making it easier for them to remember both the information and the related vocabulary.

Moreover, it has been proposed that the visuals employed in imagery mnemonics should be vivid and clear. However, some even argue that these images could be bizarre, ridiculous, or absurd (Wills, 2021). Evidence for this claim is based on research by Runge, Craig, and Jim (2015), which suggested that instructions to produce bizarre mental images improved recall performance when compared with standard learning instructions.

With respect to learning styles, one theory supporting the use of Image-Based Mnemonics is the VARK (Visual, Auditory, Reading/Writing, and Kinesthetic) learning styles theory, which categorizes learners based on their preferred sensory modalities for processing information (Husmann & O'Loughlin, 2018).

In fact, a study conducted at Dela Paz National High School in Antipolo City, led by Marino and Caballes (2022), found that among 238 learners, the most dominant type was visual learners. The study suggests that teachers use visual materials to cater to these learners. Similarly, Magulod (2018) revealed that students at Cagayan State University preferred visual learning styles in applied sciences courses, recommending the use of graphical approaches to

support these learners. Comparably, in Leyte, Englis (2019) demonstrated that the majority of students at Palompon Institute of Technology-Tabango Camp are visual learners. Similarly, in Apayao, students at state colleges showed a preference for visual learning, with 46 percent supporting this style. Additionally, a local study conducted at Bukidnon State University by Lumanog (2016) found that the predominant learning styles among students were visual and auditory.

In the context of academic disciplines, the field of science is often filled with novel terms and complex concepts, such as those found in physics, which students may find overwhelming to absorb and understand. In the Philippines, many students exhibit a negative attitude towards learning physics, which can be attributed to several factors, including challenges in solving problems that involve calculations and a lack of motivation to actively participate in class (Guido, 2013). Furthermore, some students link their negative attitudes towards physics to a teacher's lack of enthusiasm, a personal lack of interest in the subject, a generally negative perception of the subject, low self-confidence, and difficulties in solving physics problems (Tazitabong, 2018).

Given this context, the researchers were dedicated to focusing on improving the vocabulary learning of the students in physics to have a better comprehension of the lesson and simplifying the lesson into chunks that are way simpler for them to learn.

In summary, the literature review highlights the critical role of vocabulary skills within the realm of science education, emphasizing their importance for students struggling with complex scientific terminologies. Mnemonic strategies, identified as valuable tools, proved essential in facilitating the mastery of complex scientific language. One particular strategy, the use of Image-Based Mnemonics, was examined and found useful in making science learning a more accessible and engaging experience by adopting a visual and memorable approach that caters to diverse learning preferences, particularly benefiting visual learners. This personalized and impactful method enhances comprehension and retention of scientific information.

Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study employed Creswell's (2013) multiphase mixed-method design, incorporating descriptive quantitative research, pretest-posttest with a non-equivalent control group, and sequential explanatory mixed-method research.

In the first phase, a descriptive method was used to outline the pretest and posttest scores of both the control and experimental groups, helping to identify trends and differences and offering insights into the effectiveness of the experimental conditions.

Transitioning to the second phase, the study employed a quasi-experimental, non-equivalent control group design, comparing a treatment group with a non-equivalent control group without random assignment (Bulus, 2021). The effectiveness of IBM was assessed by

comparing pretest and posttest scores between the control and experimental groups, as well as evaluating differences in their posttest scores.

In the third phase, researchers used an explanatory sequential mixed-method design. Initially, a descriptive quantitative approach assessed learners' perceptions post-exposure to Image-Based Mnemonics, followed by a phenomenological qualitative investigation to understand learners' perceptions based on their experiences and how these mnemonics influenced their acquisition of physics vocabulary skills. This combination of methods offered a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under study.

Sampling Method

Since face-to-face selection of respondents was favorable during the field study training of the researchers, the study employed purposive sampling. This non-probability technique involves choosing units based on specific traits required in the sample (Brus, 2022), allowing for a targeted and intentional selection of participants.

Respondents

The identification and selection of respondents did not rely on the distribution of pretests; instead, a purposeful selection was made. Two heterogeneous Grade 7 classes at John J. Russell Memorial High School were chosen: 7-Aluminum (52 students) served as the control group, while 7-Copper (50 students) served as the experimental group. Sections were selected based on their heterogeneity and shared afternoon schedules. Additionally, the researchers ensured that the assessment results of two students from 7-Aluminum would not be included to maintain equal respondent numbers, further ensuring similar characteristics between the groups and minimizing external factors. Furthermore, the researchers intentionally avoided selecting a pilot class to prevent potential biases during the study.

Instruments

The effectiveness of using Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM) as a supplementary learning tool to enhance learners' vocabulary skills in physics was measured using 30-item researcher-made pretests and posttests.

A general pretest was not suitable for dissemination to the students because the lesson covered three major topics. Therefore, in the first week, the researchers used a 10-item pretest focusing on the first major topic (Module 3: Sound) as an assessment tool for both the control and experimental groups. After collecting the pretest scores, the researchers employed Image-Based Mnemonics in the experimental group, while conventional teaching methods were used in the control group. Upon completing the entire topic, a 10-item posttest was administered to both groups.

This process was repeated in the second and third weeks, covering two additional major physics topics (Module 4: Light and Module 6: Electricity) identified as the least learned

competencies by Grade 7 and 8 learners' Regional Diagnostic Assessment. By following this procedure, three sets of pretest and posttest scores were generated for both the control and experimental groups. These scores were then combined to produce one general 30-item pretest and posttest score for the respondents.

For the descriptive part of the study, particularly on students' perceptions of Image-Based Mnemonics, the researchers adapted a four-point Likert-scale-based questionnaire from Whitescarver's (2018) study, "Effect of Mnemonics on the Vocabulary Acquisition and Retention of High School Students with Learning Disabilities." This adapted questionnaire comprised 10-item statements with responses including "Strongly Disagree" (1), "Disagree" (2), "Agree" (3), and "Strongly Agree" (4), focusing on the respondents' satisfaction with the use of mnemonics in vocabulary acquisition and retention.

Additionally, for the qualitative part of the study, the researchers devised an interview guide for the learners consisting of two questions, which include: (1) Did you enjoy the integration of IBM in our discussion? Why or why not? (*Nasiyahan ka ba sa paggamit ng IBM sa discussion? Bakit o bakit hindi? Ipaliwanag ang iyong sagot.*) and (2) What is your perception of the integration of IBM in science lessons? (*Ano ang iyong pananaw/opinyon sa paggamit ng IBM sa mga lesson sa science?*).

Classroom Intervention Implementation

Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM), the strategy employed by the researchers, underwent various processes before development.

Initially, the researchers selected important physics terms to be covered in each lesson, focusing on those identified as least learned based on the RDA results.

Following this, Image-Based Mnemonics were devised. During the design phase, the researchers emphasized certain principles, ensuring that subjects or characters needing focus were depicted dramatically or in a memorable manner. Sketches were carefully contextualized, and colors were chosen to be both pleasing to the eye and authentic.

Lastly, IBM was integrated into the teaching-learning process according to specific guidelines. Prior to each lesson, the corresponding IBM was displayed on the board, prompting student engagement. During discussions, the images were analyzed and interpreted, aiding comprehension. These images were then reused during subsequent lessons for recall before introducing the new IBM for motivation. The experimental group utilized IBM approximately four times a week, covering three major physics topics in the third quarter, aligned with the class schedule.

To validate the Image-Based Mnemonics developed, a junior high school Master Teacher I in science reviewed them. This ensured accuracy and alignment with the Grade 7 science curriculum's required competencies."

Figure 1.

The Sample Image-Based Mnemonics Used in Each of the Topics in Science

Decibel (dB)

Dispersion

Repulsion

Research Ethics Consideration

The researchers maintained high ethical standards by avoiding biases, preventing dishonesty, and respecting all participants. They meticulously followed protocols and guidelines to ensure the study's validity and reliability. The school heads and cooperating teacher were informed about the study's conduct following DO 16, s. 2017, or the Research Management Guidelines (RMG). Learners signed written consent forms, agreeing to be interviewed and participate in the research, and were fully informed about the study's objectives, methods, and conclusions. The researchers also ensured that confidentiality was maintained to protect student identities and privacy. After the study, other students were given the opportunity to employ strategies aimed at enhancing their vocabulary skills in physics, thus ensuring equitable access to these strategies.

Data Collection

Scores from the pre- and post-assessments were recorded, and the responses from the

interview guide were consolidated. The results of the 30-item researcher-made pretests and posttests were analyzed and recorded based on the following scale: Excellent (E) for scores ranging from 25 to 30, Proficient (P) for scores from 19 to 24, Competent (C) for scores from 13 to 18, Basic (B) for scores from 7 to 12, and Needs Improvement (NI) for scores ranging from 0 to 6.

To gauge learners' perceptions based on their experiences with the use of IBM, an interview guide was disseminated. Additionally, the class was photographed during the strategy implementation and assessments, in accordance with the agreement outlined in the signed consent form and with permission from the school administrators.

Data Analysis

The data collected in the course of this study were tabulated and analyzed using Microsoft Excel and the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The researchers employed descriptive statistics to outline the pretest and posttest scores of both the control and experimental groups, as well as to describe the learners' perceptions of Image-Based Mnemonics. A dependent sample t-test was used to determine any significant differences between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group, while an independent sample t-test was conducted to identify significant differences between the posttest scores of the control group and the experimental group, both at a 0.05 alpha level. Lastly, to delve deeper into the learners' perceptions based on their experiences with using Image-Based Mnemonics in science lessons, the researchers qualitatively analyzed the data using thematic analysis and open and axial coding. These methods allowed for the presentation of themes, theme clusters, and formulated meanings, providing a structured approach to uncovering key themes within the data.

Results and Discussion

Description of Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 1 shows the summary of the pretest and posttest scores of the control and experimental groups.

From the given data on pretest scores for the control group from 7-Aluminum, it is evident that 9 out of 50 students, or 18%, scored between 0 and 10, falling under the description "Needs Improvement". Additionally, 38 students, or 76%, scored between 7 and 12, classified as "Basic", while 3 students, or 6%, were rated as "Competent", with scores ranging from 13 to 18. Conversely, none of the students in the control group achieved scores within the ranges of 19-24 (Proficient) or 25-30 (Excellent). The average pretest score for the control group is 9, which corresponds to the "Basic" category.

Moreover, the pretest scores of the experimental group from 7-Copper reveal that only 1 out of 50 students, or 2%, scored between 0-10, falling under the "Needs Improvement"

category. Meanwhile, 33 students, or 66%, scored between 7-12, which is categorized as "Basic". Additionally, 16 students, or 32%, scored between 13-18, placing them in the "Competent" category. On the other hand, none of the students in the experimental group achieved scores in the ranges of 19-24 (Proficient) or 25-30 (Excellent). The average pretest score for the experimental group is 11.14, which can be described as "Basic".

Table 1.

Summary of Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

Pretest Scores					Posttest Scores				
Control Group (N = 50)			Experimental Group (N = 50)		Control Group (N = 50)		Experimental Group (N = 50)		
Range	f	pct.	f	pct.	f	pct.	f	pct.	
25-30	0	0.00 %	0	0.00 %	0	0.00 %	8	16.0 %	
19-24	0	0.00 %	0	0.00 %	2	4.00 %	36	72.0 %	
13-18	3	6.00 %	16	32.0 %	41	82.0 %	6	12.0 %	
7-12	38	76.0 %	33	66.0 %	7	14.0 %	0	0.00 %	
0-6	9	18.0 %	1	2.00 %	0	0.00 %	0	0.00 %	
Mean	9		11.4		14.56		21.52		
VD	Basic		Basic		Competent		Proficient		

LEGEND: *Excellent, E (25 - 30); Proficient, P (19 - 24); Competent, C (13 - 18); Basic, B (7 - 12); and Needs Improvement, NI (0 - 6)*

On the other hand, the posttest results of the control group revealed that 7 students, or 14%, scored between 7-12, earning a verbal description of "Basic". Meanwhile, 41 students, or 82%, fell into the "Competent" category, with scores ranging from 13-18. Additionally, 2 students, or 4%, were classified as "Proficient" based on their scores. Notably, no students from the control group scored between 0-6 (Needs Improvement) or between 25-30 (Excellent). Furthermore, the average posttest score of the control group was 14.56, which corresponds to the "Competent" level.

Furthermore, the posttest scores of the experimental group revealed that 6 students, or 12%, achieved scores ranging from 13-18, which is described as "Competent". Additionally, 36 students, or 72%, fell into the "Proficient" category with scores ranging from 19-24, and 8 students, or 16%, were rated as "Excellent" with scores from 25-30. Notably, none of the students in the experimental group received scores between 0-6, which indicates "Needs Improvement", or between 7-12, categorized as "Basic". Meanwhile, the average posttest score of the experimental group was 21.52, which can be described as "Proficient".

This summary presents similar findings to those of Rodriguez and Smith's (2020) study, which investigated the impact of Image-Based Mnemonics on the academic performance of elementary students. The results showed that the posttest scores of students who were exposed to Image-Based Mnemonics were significantly higher than those of students who were not exposed to this method. Specifically, the experimental group demonstrated an average score increase of 25% compared to the control group.

Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group

Table 2 presents the difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group.

As shown in Table 2, the respondents' posttest scores were observed to be higher than their pretest scores after the integration of the strategy, Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM). The pretest recorded a mean score of 11.140, while the posttest recorded a mean score of 21.520, indicating that the vocabulary skills of the students in physics improved significantly after the integration of IBM.

Table 2.

Dependent Samples T-test of Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Experimental Group

	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Pretest Scores		11.140			Highly	Reject the
Posttest Scores	50	21.520	-32.000	.000	Significant Difference	null hypothesis

* *Computed p-value is highly significant at $p < 0.005$*

Meanwhile, the calculated t-value was found to be -32.000 (absolute value = ± 32), which is far beyond the critical t-value of 2.0096. This indicates an extremely significant difference between the scores, suggesting that the observed difference is very unlikely to be due to random chance alone. This significant t-value suggests a notable difference between the test variables in the study, and therefore, the null hypothesis must be rejected.

In addition, the p-value of the data set ($p = 0.000$) provides additional support, indicating that the difference between the pretest and posttest results is highly significant. With this result, it can be concluded that the integration of Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM) in teaching has had a positive impact on the vocabulary skills of the students in Physics.

Based on the study of Tayyebi (2021), it was revealed that the use of Image-Based Mnemonics in vocabulary learning resulted in enhanced cognitive activity, more extensive processing, and higher retention in vocabulary learning, suggesting that visual aids play a critical role in memory enhancement.

Likewise, Mastropieri and Scruggs (2021) discovered that image mnemonics served as a valuable tool in establishing connections between new words and previously acquired

information.

Difference Between the Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 3 presents the results of the independent samples t-test comparing the posttest scores of the control and experimental groups. It includes the number of respondents, mean, t-value, p-value, and an interpretation of the analysis.

The posttest scores of the experimental group were shown to be higher than those of the control group. Specifically, the control group had a mean posttest score of 14.560, whereas the experimental group had a mean posttest score of 21.520. This result indicates that the learners' vocabulary skills in physics improved more significantly in the group exposed to the IBM strategy compared to the group that was not.

Table 3.

Independent Samples T-test of Posttest Scores of the Control and Experimental Groups

	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Control Group	50	14.560	-13.525	.000	Highly Significant Difference	Reject the null hypothesis
Experimental Group		21.520				

* *Computed p-value is highly significant at $p < 0.005$*

In addition, the calculated t-value was -13.525 (absolute value = ± 13.525), which is far beyond the critical t-value of 1.9845. This indicates an extremely significant difference between the scores of the groups, suggesting that the observed difference is very unlikely to be due to random chance alone. This significant t-value suggests a notable difference between the test variables in the study, and therefore, the null hypothesis must be rejected.

It was further supported by the p-value of the data set ($p = 0.000$), indicating that the difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental groups is highly significant. Based on this result, it can be inferred that the integration of Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM) in teaching can serve as a valuable supplementary learning tool for enhancing learners' vocabulary skills in physics.

According to a study by Lu Pan (2021), the use of Image-Based Mnemonics significantly enhances vocabulary retention among students by providing visual associations that aid in memory recall. Similarly, Cioca and Nerisanu (2020) proved in their study that the application of Image-Based Mnemonics in science significantly improves students' vocabulary retention, aiding in the understanding of complex scientific terms through visual representation.

Description of Learners' Perceptions Towards the Use of Image-Based Mnemonics

Table 4 shows the summary of learners' perceptions towards the use of Image-Based Mnemonics.

Accordingly, item number 2 obtained the highest mean response (i.e., “Strongly Agree”; $\bar{x} = 3.880$). This indicates that students “strongly agree” that it is easier to memorize and remember vocabulary definitions when using IBM. In contrast, the lowest mean response was for item number 5 (i.e., “Disagree”; $\bar{x} = 2.366$), suggesting that students “disagree” that they will be able to easily create IBM for personal use.

Table 4.

Summary of Learners' Perceptions Towards the Use of Image-Based Mnemonics

Statements	Mean (N = 50)	VD
1. I prefer using Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM) to memorize vocabulary words.	3.320	SA
2. It is easier to memorize and remember vocabulary definitions when using IBM.	3.880	SA
3. I find myself focusing more on the vocabulary that is associated with the pictures that are more unusual.	3.800	SA
4. I think I will use this strategy in the future.	3.540	SA
5. I think I will be able to easily create IBM for personal use.	2.366	D
6. I believe I was able to remember more when using IBM.	3.840	SA
7. I observed that I remember lessons easily with the use of IBM.	3.440	SA
8. I break down large information into small and easy-to-remember information because of mnemonics.	3.080	A
9. Using IBM helps me recall vocabulary better than other conventional methods.	3.640	SA
10. Associating IBM with vocabulary in class made me more excited to learn vocabulary words in physics.	3.140	A
Overall Mean	3.405	SA

LEGEND: *Strongly Agree, SA (3.25 - 4.00); Agree, A (2.50 - 3.24); Disagree, D (1.75 - 2.49); and Strongly Disagree, SD (1.75 - 2.49)*

Generally, the respondents' mean answers were either “Strongly Agree” ($\bar{x} = 3.880$) or “Disagree” ($\bar{x} = 2.366$) to all items related to students' satisfaction with the use of Image-Based Mnemonics. The overall mean was 3.405, indicating that students exposed to the integration of Image-Based Mnemonics were highly satisfied and enjoyed the process.

It is concluded in the account of Tayyebi (2021) that when the researcher used imagery mnemonics in vocabulary learning, it resulted in enhanced cognitive activity, more extensive processing, and higher retention in vocabulary learning. This approach not only facilitated memory recall but also engaged learners in a more interactive and visually stimulating manner. Moreover, Tullis (2021) stated that mnemonics is a memory technique that helps the brain to encode and recall significant information, in addition to the fact that the retention percentages of vocabulary paired with mnemonics were higher than for those words taught through traditional methods.

Learners' Perception Based on their Experiences with Using Image-Based Mnemonics

Using thematic analysis, the responses of the learners to the interview guide were segregated into themes, as displayed in Table 5. Two questions were asked to the randomly selected 10 learners, who were allowed to respond freely, and their responses were analyzed thematically. This analysis generated main themes and sub-themes to clearly organize the learners' feedback. From their comments, three main themes and nine sub-themes emerged.

Table 5.

Learners' Perceptions Based on their Experiences with the Use of Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM) In Science Lessons

Questions	Themes	Theme Clusters	Formulated Meanings
Did you enjoy the integration of IBM in our discussion? Why or why not?	Enhanced Learning Engagement	Clear Understanding of the Lesson, Catches Attention, Enjoyable, and Interactive	Integrating IBM into lessons aids learners to comprehend the lesson better while also having a lively discussion, fostering a lively learning experience and active student participation.
What is your perception of the integration of IBM in science lessons?	Helpful	Concept Comprehension, Enhances Critical Thinking Skills, and Encourages Collaborative Learning	Integrating IBM helps learners comprehend physics concepts more easily, provides time for brainstorming ideas, and encourages collaboration with classmates and peers.
	IBM as a Motivation	Exciting Learning and Engaging Learning	The use of IBMs in lessons excites learners with engaging pictures, encouraging them to participate in discussions as they enjoy observing and analyzing the visuals.

Main Theme 1: Enhanced Learning Engagement

The integration of Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM) in science lessons has been found to positively affect students by fostering a clear understanding of the lesson, capturing their attention, providing enjoyment, and encouraging interactive discussions. Some comments were:

S#4

"opo, dahil mas madali naming maipaliwanag at ma-gets yung terms dahil sa mga pictures." (Yes, because we can easily explain and understand the terms in the lesson thanks to the pictures.)

S#3

"Oo, nakakatuwang tingnan ang mga pictures. Hindi boring ang discussion ni sir dahil maganda ang mga pictures at nakukuha nito ang attention namin" (Yes, it is fun to observe the pictures presented. The discussion never got boring because the pictures were pleasing and could catch our attention.)

S#7

"opo, dahil nakakatuwang pag-aralan ang lesson dahil sa mga IBM." (Yes, because the lessons are enjoyable to study, thanks to IBM.)

S#8

"opo, kase hindi boring ang klase, nalalaman agad namin ang lesson na itinuturo kaya nakakasagot ako" (Yes, because the class is never boring. We can easily learn the lesson being taught, which is why I can participate in the discussion.)

From the statements of the learners, the integration of Image-Based Mnemonics (IBMs) in their lessons could be regarded as having a positive impact. The responses showed that they enjoyed lessons incorporating IBMs, which helped them understand the lessons clearly, captured their attention, were enjoyable, and facilitated interactivity.

A study by Kusumawati, Syarief, and Cahyono (2020) investigated the effectiveness of employing images, including IBMs, in vocabulary instruction for seventh-grade students. Their findings showed similar results, indicating that the use of images notably enhanced students' comprehension of vocabulary. This underscores the potential efficacy of IBMs as valuable tools for facilitating students' understanding of lesson materials.

Furthermore, incorporating IBMs not only facilitates a clear understanding of the lesson content but also cultivates an engaging and interactive learning environment. This observation aligns with the findings of Kozmus and Kozmus (2023), whose study demonstrated a significant enhancement in memory performance and overall learning experience through the use of IBMs. Their research also revealed that integrating IBMs heightened interactivity and enjoyment during lessons, further accentuating its effectiveness as a pedagogical tool.

Main Theme 2: Helpful and IBM as a Motivation

Learners appreciated the integration of image-based mnemonics in science lessons, as these strategies were helpful and served as a form of motivation. Consequently, IBMs helped learners understand the lesson clearly, enhanced their critical thinking skills, encouraged collaborative learning, and fostered an exciting and engaging learning environment. Some of the learners' comments were:

S#5

“Madaling magkabisa ng mga terms kapag may IBM kase mas naiintindihan ko ang pinag aaralan namin” (It is easier for me to memorize science terms and comprehend the lesson if there are IBMs present.)

S#7

“nakakatulong po ang IBM at saka binibigyan kami ni ser ng time para isipin muna kung ano ang ibig sabihin ng IBM na ipinapakita nya” (IBM is helpful, and our teacher gives us time to think and give our ideas first about the presented IBM.)

S#1

“gusto ko ang ibm at saka nagiging excited ako sa mga susunod na lessons kase gusto kong makita kung ano pang pictures ang pag aaralan namin” (I like IBM, and it makes me excited about the next lessons, as I want to know the next set of pictures to be presented and studied.)

S#8

“masaya kapag may IBM na kasama sa lesson ni ser dahil gustong gusto ko na sumagot kasi ito ay masaya” (It makes me happy whenever there is an IBM included in the discussion because it makes me eager to participate more.)

These statements indicate that learners greatly appreciated the integration of IBMs in science class, finding them helpful and motivating, which created an exciting and engaging learning environment. In fact, Grantham, Jarman, and Hiester (2019) found a significant improvement in critical thinking skills among students who used Image-Based Mnemonics compared to those who did not, while Bailey, Elferink, and Gow (2016) discovered that students using visual mnemonics demonstrated higher levels of collaboration and engagement. Similarly, Paton (2020) explored the effects of visual mnemonics on vocabulary retention among Japanese students and found that these students not only retained vocabulary more effectively but also reported higher levels of engagement and motivation.

In summary, positive perceptions from the learners were collected, which affirmed the effectiveness of Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM) as a supplementary learning tool for enhancing vocabulary skills in physics. However, the present findings may still be pursued in other settings and should proceed with further validation using a large sample size.

Conclusion

The study's findings demonstrated the influence of Image-Based Mnemonics (IBM) on the significant vocabulary skills improvement of Grade 7 learners. It is evident from the fact that the learners in the experimental group exhibited significant improvement after exposure to IBM, achieving higher posttest scores than the control group. Additionally, Grade 7 learners who were exposed to IBM reported high levels of satisfaction and enjoyment in the learning process, which reflected on their responses to the interview guide.

Moreover, the integration of IBM in science classes proved to be beneficial, enjoyable, and motivating for learners. Overall, the use of IBM as a supplementary learning strategy has a highly promising impact on enhancing learners' vocabulary skills in physics upon integration into the lesson.

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